

Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II), Dioxouranium(VI) and Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes with 2-(*N*- α -Benzyl-2-hydroxybenzylideneimino)- ethane Sulphonic Acid

ASHOK GAHLOT, (Miss) SHOBHA SHARMA and R. K. MEHTA*

Chemistry Department, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 6 March 1985, revised 31 July 1985, accepted 2 December 1985

The dissociation constants of 2-(*N*- α -benzyl-2-hydroxybenzylideneimino)ethane sulphonic acid (H_2BE) and stability constants of its chelates with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , $U^{VI}O_2$ and $V^{IV}O$ have been determined in aqueous medium ($\mu = 0.1 M$) at 25, 35 and 45° using Calvin's extension of Bjerrum's method. Values of ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° of the chelates have been evaluated. Elemental analysis, molecular weight, electronic and ir spectra, magnetic moments and conductance of the solid complexes indicate an octahedral stereochemistry for these chelates except those of the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} which possesses a tetrahedral geometry.

THE stability constants of the chelates of 2-(*N*- α -benzyl-2-hydroxybenzylideneimino)ethane sulphonic acid (H_2BE) with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , $U^{VI}O_2$ and $V^{IV}O$ have been evaluated using Calvin's extension of Bjerrum's method^{1,2}.

Experimental

2-(*N*- α -Benzyl-2-hydroxybenzylideneimino)ethane sulphonic acid (H_2BE) was synthesised by the method reported earlier³, m.p. 180° (Found ; C, 58.90 ; H, 4.19 ; N, 4.56 ; S, 10.42. $C_{15}H_{13}NSO_4$ calcd. for : C, 59.40 ; H, 4.29 ; N, 4.62 ; S, 10.56%).

The following mixtures (total volume 40 ml) were prepared and titrated against carbonate-free 0.1M sodium hydroxide solution at 25, 35 and 45° in nitrogen atmosphere and the titration curves are found to be of the usual shapes : (A) 10.0 ml 0.01M H_2BE + 4.0 ml 1.0M $NaClO_4$ + 26.0 ml water ; (B) 10.0 ml 0.01M H_2BE + 4.0 ml 1.0M $NaClO_4$ + 10.0 ml 0.01M metal ion solution + 16.0 ml water ; (C) 20.0 ml 0.01M H_2BE + 4.0 ml 1.0M $NaClO_4$ + 10.0 ml 0.01M metal ion solution + 6.0 ml water.

Results and Discussion

The pK_1 and pK_2 values of the H_2BE are found to be 7.92 and 10.02 at 25°, 7.40 and 9.74 at 35°, and 6.95 and 9.21 at 45°, respectively. These values suggest that H_2BE is a biprotic ligand. The metal-ligand stability constants are read from the formation curves drawn by plotting $\bar{n}$ vs $-\log [A^-]$. The refinement is done by the computational methods⁴ and the values obtained by different methods are in agreement and their average values are summarised in Table 1. The

order of stability found, $V^{IV}O > U^{VI}O_2 > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II}$, is in accordance with Irving-Williams rule⁵.

Thermodynamic functions : The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) have been evaluated using Gibbs-Helmholtz equation⁶ (Table 1). ΔG° values of all the chelates are more negative at 45° than at lower temperature. It is further observed that ΔH° is positive in all cases, which suggests endothermic nature of reactions. The positive values of ΔS° indicate that entropy term is favourable for their formation.

Solid chelates :

Preparation : The solid metal chelates were synthesised by refluxing a mixture of metal nitrate (0.01M in 15 to 20 ml 75% ethanol) and H_2BE (0.01M in 25 to 50 ml 75% ethanol) for 2-3 h in nitrogen atmosphere. On concentrating the mixture, the coloured precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried (~70%). All the metal chelates were synthesised by this method.

The solid metal chelates do not possess sharp melting points, and decompose on heating between 250 to 280°. These compounds were analysed for C, H, N, S, metal and water (Table 2). Their molecular weights were determined ebulliometrically. From these data it is evident that the metal chelates exist as monomer in the solid state and possess 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry.

The solid Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , and $V^{IV}O$ chelates are found paramagnetic (Table 1) and the rest diamagnetic. On crystallisation, the composition of the metal chelates remains unaltered.

TABLE 1—AVERAGE STABILITY CONSTANTS THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF METAL CHELATES OF 2-(N- α -BENZYL-2-HYDROXYBENZYLIDINEIMINO)ETHANE SULPHONIC ACID (H₂BE)

Metal ion	Stability constant			- ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹			ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} at 303 K B.M.	
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	at 35°			
Co ^{II}	log K ₁	5.80	6.35	7.48	64.87	70.23	73.43	62.60	24.77	4.45
	log K ₂	3.95	4.95	5.30						
Ni ^{II}	log K ₁	6.30	7.05	8.15	71.49	76.01	80.98	69.85	20.00	2.93
	log K ₂	4.65	5.50	6.45						
Cu ^{II}	log K ₁	7.10	7.65	8.18	79.02	32.44	86.89	38.10	14.39	1.88
	log K ₂	5.15	6.10	6.85						
Zn ^{II}	log K ₁	4.38	5.95	7.10	33.03	35.32	37.14	28.12	23.37	—
	log K ₂	—	—	—						
Cd ^{II}	log K ₁	3.75	4.95	6.35	30.07	31.55	33.42	19.93	37.66	—
	log K ₂	—	—	—						
U ^{VI} O ₂	log K ₁	7.32	8.15	8.50	81.42	88.16	92.24	79.83	27.04	—
	log K ₂	5.80	6.65	7.15						
V ^{IV} O	log K ₁	8.10	8.65	9.13	85.36	92.53	96.81	85.28	23.53	1.69
	log K ₂	6.35	6.95	7.70						

TABLE 2—YIELD, MOLECULAR WEIGHT, ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND CONDUCTANCE OF H₂BE AND ITS HYDRATED METAL CHELATES

Compd.	Yield %	Molecular weight	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					ΔM	
			C	H	N	S	Metal	Water	Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
[Co(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NSO ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂]	67	409 (416)	3.56 (3.60)	4.40 (4.56)	3.31 (3.36)	7.61 (7.69)	14.11 (14.18)	12.95 (12.98)	3.0
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NSO ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂]	72	406 (415)	3.58 (3.61)	4.51 (4.57)	3.29 (3.37)	7.68 (7.71)	13.91 (13.79)	12.93 (13.01)	4.7
[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NSO ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂]	81	411 (420)	3.50 (3.57)	4.48 (4.52)	3.31 (3.33)	7.53 (7.63)	14.88 (15.00)	12.83 (12.85)	6.0
[Zn(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NSO ₄)(H ₂ O)]	68	376 (386)	3.76 (3.88)	3.70 (3.88)	3.53 (3.62)	8.19 (8.29)	16.79 (16.83)	4.56 (4.66)	3.7
[Cd(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NSO ₄)(H ₂ O)]	76	427 (433)	3.40 (3.46)	3.42 (3.46)	3.17 (3.23)	7.29 (7.39)	25.76 (25.86)	4.07 (4.15)	3.8
[UO ₂ (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NSO ₄)(H ₂ O)]	72	583 (591)	2.51 (2.53)	2.49 (2.53)	2.28 (2.36)	5.33 (5.41)	40.21 (40.27)	3.02 (3.04)	6.7
[VO(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NSO ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂]	63	398 (406)	3.58 (3.69)	4.10 (4.18)	3.39 (3.44)	7.78 (7.88)	12.49 (12.56)	8.80 (8.86)	8.6

* Calculated values in parenthesis

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra in benzene of the Co^{II} chelate consist of two bands at 8 650 and 22 000 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to the transitions ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P), respectively. These bands suggest an octahedral stereochemistry for the Co^{II} chelate. The spectra for the Ni^{II} chelate show two bands at 13 650 and 26 400 cm⁻¹ assignable to the transitions ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P), respectively. These bands suggest an octahedral stereochemistry around Ni^{II} ion^{7,8}. In the case of Cu^{II} chelate, a broad absorption band at 12 810 cm⁻¹ is observed which may be due to the transition ³E_g → ³T_{2g}. It suggests an octahedral stereochemistry for Cu^{II} chelate. The V^{IV}O chelate shows two bands at 11 570 and 18 700 cm⁻¹ assignable to the transitions d_{xy} → d_{xy}, d_{yz} and d_{xz} → d_{xz}, respectively in an octahedral environment of VO²⁺.

Ir spectra: Ir spectra of H₂BE show bands at 3 260, 1 610 and 1 190 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{OH} ,

ν_{CN} and ν_{SO_2OH} , respectively. ν_{CN} of H₂BE around 1 610 cm⁻¹ is shifted to lower frequency side on complexation, indicating participation of the azomethine nitrogen in coordination. In the metal chelates, two new bands in the ranges 400-420 and 580-600 cm⁻¹ suggest the formation of M-N and M-O bonds in them. All the complexes give one broad band in the region 3 200-3 230 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} of the water molecule. The loss of water molecules at relatively high temperature (>180°) indicates that these are coordinated and not lattice field.

It appears that due to steric factors, 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry is not attended. In view of the experimental evidences received, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, U^{VI}O₂ and V^{IV}O chelates may be assigned an octahedral stereochemistry, whereas Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} chelates are tetrahedral as is common with these ions. These structures are represented in Fig. 1.

When $n = 1$, $M(II) = Zn, Cd$ or UO_2
 $n = 2$, $M(II) = VO$
 $n = 3$, $M(II) = Co, Ni$ or Cu .

Fig. 1. Bivalent metal chelate of 2-(*N*- α -benzyl-2-hydroxybenzylidene)ethane sulphonic acid (H_2BE).

References

1. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.

2. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
 3. P. MEHTA and R. K. MEHTA, *Proc. Indian Natl. Sci. Acad., Sect. A*, 1984, 50, 69.
 4. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3397.
 5. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
 6. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASILES, "Instability Constant of Complex Compounds", Van Nostrand, New York, 1960, p. 63.
 7. M. C. DAY and J. SELVIN, "Theoretical Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1962, p. 325.
 8. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968, p. 333.
 9. J. SELVIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 165.